

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and
Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Data Management Plan
Deliverable D7.3**

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ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.3

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<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

This deliverable is the second version of the Data Management Plan of the project. It is the revision of D7.2 submitted in June 2023 where the initial plan was set up. It will be revised at Month 47 (D7.4 - Final update of data management plan).

2. Conclusion & Results

The main conclusions of this deliverable are that the data produced within the project, even if not kept, will be obtained with version-controlled software (kept in the partners git repositories) ensuring the reproducibility and FAIRness of the data and that we will follow the GDPR rules when gathering personal data

3. Project objectives

This deliverable has a special status compared with the rest of the deliverables and milestones of the project, as it reports on the data management and not the actual scientific or technical results of the project. This deliverable rather describes the compliance with the rules of data management according to the main guidelines of the European commission.

4. Project data and software

4.1 Data Summary

As anticipated in the first version of the data management plan, no long-term numerical data has been generated in the project, every output being only temporal results stored individually by each partner on their premises. The main outcome of the project is the software which is currently stored, and version controlled in the open access partners repositories (Github, Gitlab, or the in-house model repositories).

In Work Package 1 “Support to effective applications”, the BSC mixed precision software is available in the internal BSC Earth Sciences department github¹, the HPCW is hosted in the DKRZ Gitlab, while ecTrans, cloudsc, ecRad, NICAMDC are stored in Github, ICON is stored in the DKRZ Gitlab, and Nemo is stored in its own repo at NEMO workspace². All these repositories ensure the proper FAIRness³ (openness and version control) of the data.

All the documentation produced in Work Packages 5 (“Training and capacity building”) and 6 (“Community engagement, dissemination and exploitation”) is stored in the CSC Github for the training materials and in the GDPR-compliant system of CSC for the personal data of the participants to the hackathons. The material for the EuroCC training sprint with Austria NCC is also on a public Github page.

The “Community engagement, dissemination and exploitation” and “Project Management” Work Packages (6 and 7) have been using the BSC servers to store the data. In this case, the data consists of forms, presentations, mailing lists, deliverables and milestones. The BSC servers are GDPR compliant, and they include the wiki (restricted to the consortium partners) of the project among other platforms. The deliverables have been uploaded to the EU participant portal and at the moment of writing part of the presentations and deliverables have been uploaded to Zenodo where they have been given DOIs. One of the objectives of the next release of the DMP is to reach a full store all the public documents produced by EsiWACE3 in Zenodo, including public milestones, deliverables, scientific publications and presentations.

Dissemination campaigns from WP6 which ran in the social media (X, LinkedIn, Youtube,...) were based on previous signing of personal consent form for each participant.

¹<https://earth.bsc.es/gitlab/ces/hpc-for-es-team/esiwace3-openifs-m7>,

²<https://forge.nemo-ocean.eu/nemo>

³<https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

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4.2 FAIR data

Considering the absence of numerical data, the data FAIRness⁴ (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) in the context of the project has been discussed but was considered not applicable in the first deliverable. However, the data mentioned in section 4.1 can be considered FAIR because of its Findability and Accessibility at least.

4.3 Other research outputs

Not applicable.

4.4 Allocation of resources

There is no changes in the allocation of resources. What was reported in the first version of the DMP still holds.

The data management of the project is handled in Work Package 7, with the current deliverable and its two following revisions. One person from BSC will be dedicated to this work, with 2 PMs from the 33 of this Work Package.

4.5 Data security

The data security concerns here only the backup of the virtual machines hosting the gitlab, project wiki and website described in section 4.1.

4.6 Ethics

The techniques developed in this project will only utilise geophysical data/parameters obtained from numerical weather and climate model simulations. No personal or environmental data of any kind will be used. Therefore, we identify no ethical issues of any kind related to human rights and values when applying techniques related to artificial intelligence or machine learning in the framework of this project.

5. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation

5.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the audience for this deliverable is:

⁴<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

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X	The general public (PU).
X	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

5.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Not applicable.

5.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

In the first version of the data management plan, it was mentioned that we were planning to publish scientific publication in peer reviewed journals, with open access. So far, four papers have been written as results of the research done in ESiWACE3: three of them are based on the research from ESiWACE3, while the fourth (currently in review phase) explicitly acknowledges ESiWACE3. The objective for the next revision of the DMP is to have all the papers published with explicit acknowledgements to ESiWACE3.

5.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

Not applicable.